

Newsletter 04/2018

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Dissemination and Upcoming Events: Meet Us!

ESIWACE will participate in

- 5th ENES HPC workshop, 17-18 May, Lecce/Italy, www.esiwace.eu/events/5th-enes-hpc-workshop (organised by ESIWACE)
- ESCO 2018, 3-8 June, Pilsen/Czech Rep., www.esco2018.femhub.com
- Teratec Forum, 19-20 June, Palaiseau/France, <http://www.teratec.eu/gb/forum/>
- ISC 2018, 24-28 June, Frankfurt/Germany, <https://www.isc-hpc.com/>
- PASC 2018, 2-4 July, Basel/Switzerland, pasc18.pasc-conference.org
- 3rd ENES Workshop on Workflows, 13-14 September, Brussels/Belgium, <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/esiwace-workshop-on-workflows-1/esiwace-workshop-on-workflows>
- 18th ECMWF Workshop on High Performance Computing in Meteorology, 24-28 Sep, Reading/UK, www.ecmwf.int/en/learning/workshops

Support for DYAMOND

DYAMOND stands for **D**Ynamics of the **A**tmospheric general circulation **M**odeled **O**n **N**on-hydrostatic **D**omains. The project describes a framework for the inter-comparison of an emerging class of atmospheric circulation models that, through their resolution of the major modes of atmospheric heat transport, endeavor to represent the most important scales of the full three-dimensional fluid dynamics of the atmospheric circulation.

Due to the joint interest in high-resolution simulations, ESiWACE strongly supports DYAMOND by carrying out scaling and performance experiments for corresponding 5km global ICON atmosphere-only simulations. Asynchronous IO could be tuned for the ICON set up, reducing the IO to roughly 50% for large node counts (number of nodes > 500). Via MPI-M, grib output for all required variables was enabled (compared to previous NetCDF-based outputs of the ESiWACE atmosphere-only demonstrator), reducing the file sizes tremendously (factor 2-3, or even more). The DYAMOND runs currently suggest a performance of ca. 45 simulated days per (compute) day on 900 nodes of Mistral, compute2 partition (Broadwell), relying on non-hydrostatics, full IO and double precision.

For more information and for details on participation, please see the [DYAMOND website](#).

Multithreading in OASIS3-MCT

In the recent deliverable D2.3 “Multithreaded or thread safe OASIS version including performance optimizations to adapt to many-core architectures”, latest developments within the coupler OASIS3-MCT are detailed. The improvements will be available in the next release OASIS3-MCT_4.0 planned for spring 2018. A new communication method, which can now use the mapping weights to define the intermediate mapping decomposition, takes longer to initialise, but it offers significant gain at run time. The latter especially holds for high-resolution cases that run on a high number of tasks. The hybrid OpenMP-MPI parallelisation introduced in the SCRIP library for the mapping weight calculation allows a reduction in the weight calculation time of 2 to 3 orders of magnitude for high-resolution grids.

Hybrid OpenMP-MPI Developments for NEMO

The OpenMP tiling coarse-grained parallelisation of NEMO has been extended to the tracer advection scheme in order to evaluate the approach on a kernel which is more affected by the MPI communication overhead. The code has been restructured to reduce the number of parallel regions with respect to the fine-grained version. Preliminary results show an improvement at inter-node level that is comparable with the vertical physics (~7% of the parallel efficiency on 512 cores compared with the pure MPI version). The code will be further revisited in order to have a single OpenMP parallel region and to better benefit from the coarse-grained implementation.

Updates on Cylc Development and Deployment

With over 90 pull requests, the Cylc-7.6.X series had a good number of enhancements and bug fixes, including smarter client-server logic, improved usage of parameters to define and group similar tasks with less repetition, and smarter task job remote host selection and initialisation logic. Cylc has further been integrated with the data analytics cluster at CMCC to support post-processing and analysis case studies.

Updates on the Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM)

The test-driven integration of the ESDM led to a first, fully featured test from NetCDF application to POSIX storage. Additionally, the feasibility of utilising multiple storage tiers (memory, local storage, cluster file system) could be demonstrated on the supercomputer Mistral at DKRZ.

Snapshots

Bull currently works together with IPSL on NEMO optimisation; Bull will further participate in the NEMO HPC Subgroup meeting.

BSC currently addresses stability of EC-Earth on Mare Nostrum 4.

CMCC carries on work on a hybrid version of NEMO.

UREAD, STFC and DKRZ work towards the integration of further storage systems and harnessing automatic storage placing. The first of the semantic storage layer tools (s3netcdf) now has a minimal set of features for supporting sharding to, and reading from, object stores, and is in testing for performance.

ECMWF has just finished some work on data compression and submitted a corresponding manuscript for publication.

IPSL has completed OpenMP multithreading of the client part of XIOS; validations are currently pursued. Interactions with ICHEC have started on the support of GRIB2 data format for output.

MPI-M has recently published an updated version of "[The Application Software Framework \(White Paper\)](#)". Besides, work on ICON simulations in the scope of the project [DYAMOND](#) to compare global high-resolution models is in progress.

DKRZ supports MPI-M in the [DYAMOND](#) runs and further looks into performance prediction methods for various simulation scenarios and set ups.

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